

PartArt4OW

Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation Plan

Deliverable 6.1

Deliverable description

Deliverable 6.1 explains the rationale, steps and tools that will be put in place and developed for effective Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of the PartArt4OW project. It presents the strategies that will be undertaken to reach target audiences, to reach the milestones and promote the results of the project.

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Table of contents

Deliverable description	2
Acronyms	6
Summary.....	7
1. Introduction.....	8
2. Overview of the project.....	10
3. Work Package 6 Objectives.....	13
4. Target Audiences	14
5. Communication Plan	16
5.1 Objectives	16
5.2 Key Messages.....	16
5.3 Communication Channels	20
5.4 Communication Timeline	26
5.5 Open Calls Communication Campaign.....	30
5.6 Guiding principles.....	32
6. Dissemination Plan.....	35
6.1 Objectives	35
6.2 Key Dissemination Activities	36
6.3 Dissemination Channels.....	37
6.4 Dissemination Timeline	38
7. Exploitation Plan	40
7.1 Objectives	40
7.2 Key Exploitation Outputs, Activities, Pathways and Stakeholders	41
7.3 Exploitation Timeline	45
8. The Sailing Lab	47
9. KPIs and Monitoring tools	49
10. Monitoring and Evaluation	51
11. Tools and Channels	52
11.1 Visual identity.....	52
11.2 Website	52
11.3 Social media	53
11.4 ZENODO	54

11.5 Promotional materials for open calls and the Sailing Lab	54
11.6 Publications.....	55
11.7 Infographics	55
12. Final Remarks.....	56

Acronyms

EU	European Union
PAIs	Participatory Art Initiatives
UN SDG	United Nations Sustainable Development Goals
GD	Green Deal
CDE	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
WP	Work Package

Summary

Deliverable 6.1 outlines the work plan for WP6, focused on 'Communications and Dissemination'. The primary goal of this work package is to promote awareness about the three Open Calls for the PartArt4OW Accelerator program. It also seeks to communicate and disseminate the activities and results of PartArt4OW and its Accelerator pilots, while highlighting the Sailing Lab's experiences. Additionally, it includes the creation of promotional materials and engagement with key stakeholders. The document identifies target audiences, strategies, and key messages that the Consortium will share throughout the project. It also provides a detailed list of steps for communication, dissemination, and exploitation efforts. This plan serves as a roadmap to enhance the visibility of the project's activities, milestones, and results. It marks the first deliverable for WP6, which is managed by Regenera Network SL (RegNet).

1. Introduction

Effectively communicating the outcomes of an EU-funded project plays a crucial role in its overall success. It helps increase the impact of EU funding while fostering a stronger sense of European identity. This Communication Strategy, which incorporates Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) actions, aims to define the tools and necessary steps to support the project's communication efforts and raise awareness among various audiences. The goals of this plan are twofold: to offer the Consortium practical tools and guidelines to help identify and capitalise on communication opportunities throughout the project's duration; and to maximise the visibility, impact, and sustainability of the project by ensuring that its results and knowledge reach a wide range of audiences. This involves promoting the value of interdisciplinary collaboration between the **artistic, cultural, and creative sectors** and **scientific communities** in tackling ocean and water basin challenges. The strategy plans to align and coordinate actions across local, national, European, and international levels.

This plan will be evaluated twice a year, using qualitative and quantitative data from both online and offline communication efforts. Adjustments may be made as needed to ensure it remains aligned with evolving requirements.

As per an early H2020 EC document¹, the following definitions will serve as guiding principles for this strategy:

- **Communication:** aimed at reaching out to society and showing the impact and benefits of the project to them; the main focus is to inform about and promote the project and its results/success; it is addressed to multiple audiences beyond the project's own community, including media and the broad public.

¹ Making the most of your H2020 project. Boosting the impact of your project through effective communication, dissemination and exploitation. <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/3bb7278e-ebf3-11e9-9c4e-01aa75ed71a1>

- **Dissemination:** aimed at transferring knowledge and results, enabling others to use them; is focused on describing and ensuring results available for others to use; it is addressed to audiences that potentially can use the results.
- **Exploitation:** concerns the effective use of project results, turning them into concrete value and impact for society; it focuses on making concrete use of the results; it is addressed to anyone using the results inside and outside the project.

2. Overview of the project

The **PartArt4OW** project, aligned with the Horizon Europe framework, is designed to address the global environmental challenges related to ocean and water health. It emphasises the importance of building emotional and societal connections with oceans and inland waters through participatory art and creative processes. The project revolves around the Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030" and supports ocean literacy by fostering societal engagement and raising awareness about the importance of sustainable governance for water ecosystems.

PartArt4OW main objectives are:

1. **Strengthening emotional connections with oceans and waters:** PartArt4OW aims to engage European citizens with oceans and their local water bodies through participatory art initiatives. This involves collaboration with artists, communities, scientists, and stakeholders, fostering creativity to cultivate a deeper attachment to water ecosystems.
2. **Raising awareness of ocean and water challenges:** The project seeks to inform and involve citizens, artists, innovators, and policymakers in understanding critical environmental issues affecting oceans and inland waters. This is achieved by supporting art and science interdisciplinary and participatory projects that address these challenges.
3. **Developing a transdisciplinary network:** PartArt4OW focuses on creating a strong network of stakeholders, including citizens, artists, researchers, and businesses, to collectively address ocean and water-related challenges. This network aims to foster collaborative solutions and promote blue innovation and sustainable governance.

To achieve these objectives, PartArt4OW will carry out the following key activities:

- **Open Calls and Participatory Art Initiatives (PAIs):** The project supports 19 interdisciplinary art-science initiatives through open calls. Selected initiatives receive funding, mentorship, and training to develop participatory art projects that raise awareness and promote ocean and water sustainability.
- **PartArt4OW Sailing Lab:** A symbolic and physical laboratory on a sailing vessel that travels to coastal communities, documenting PAIs and engaging citizens with ocean health and marine resilience.
- **Festivals and Public Engagement:** PartArt4OW organises three festivals across Europe to showcase the outcomes of the supported projects, and to further spread awareness and engage broader audiences.
- **Toolkits and Knowledge Sharing:** The project develops a toolkit to help replicate successful participatory art-science initiatives in other European locations, promoting best practices and collaboration between the creative sectors, scientists, and local communities.
- **Ecosystem building:** this task involves creating a supportive, interconnected environment that unites the artistic, scientific, cultural, and civic sectors to work collaboratively on initiatives related to ocean and water basin challenges. This task focuses on developing relationships and facilitating exchanges between stakeholders to foster innovative, interdisciplinary approaches to sustainability. Through this effort, PartArt4OW aims to strengthen networks, improve resource-sharing, and inspire collective action, making it easier for project participants and external collaborators to sustain partnerships and knowledge exchange even after the project concludes.
- **Communication and Impact Assessment:** A strong media strategy ensures wide dissemination of visual and artistic outputs to evoke emotional and intellectual engagement with marine and water issues. The project assesses the impact of its initiatives to expand the evidence base for the role of participatory art in promoting water literacy and sustainability.

Through these efforts, PartArt4OW fosters a paradigm shift, linking communities with oceans and water bodies, encouraging sustainable behaviours, and leveraging the power of art to drive social change.

3. Work Package 6 Objectives

The main objectives of WP6: Communication and dissemination are:

- O1: Increase awareness of the general public on ocean and water-related issues
- O2: Maximise participation to the open calls and assure diversity of participants
- O3: Disseminate PAIs and project activities and results
- O4: Raise awareness on the impact and value of multidisciplinary and multisectoral collaborations for tackling ocean and water issues
- O5: Engage and connect citizens and communities.

The strategy will focus on the main streams of work of the project:

- The open calls
- The accelerators and its PAIs
- The Sailing Lab
- The ecosystem building and toolkit

4. Target Audiences

The project will disseminate news and results in a timely fashion to a broad range of stakeholders and audiences.

Artists and actors of the cultural and creative sector as well as **researchers/innovators** and **citizens/communities** and **civic society organisations** will be the main targets in the first stage of the project, for the promotion of the open calls. They will be informed about the PartArt4OW open calls, matchmaking events, and the support measures provided. When PAIs will start, and once results will become evident, they will be targeted with dedicated communication campaigns and another one will be dedicated to the PartArt4OW toolkit to support its uptake.

Policy makers, civil servants, funding agencies and philanthropies will be targeted for raising awareness on the role that the arts and creativity can have in addressing ocean and water challenges, widening the impact of research and in therefore supporting evidence-based policymaking. They will be informed about PAIs, about experimental methodologies that can be implemented and scaled-up at local level, and about the mutual learning exercise.

Finally, this group will also be a relevant recipient for the impact assessment report and the related lessons learned.

Actors in the blue economy, innovators, will be targeted to raise awareness about the role art and creativity can have, how to support them further and how to collaborate on this.

Environmental NGOs and advocacy groups will be targeted to create synergies and promote open discussions about the role of a healthy ocean in mitigating climate change, preserving biodiversity, and fostering resilient ecosystems, as well as to gather already motivated participants for the open call.

Topic-related EU projects will be reached for promoting the project's main findings and PartArt4OW events. They will be also engaged within WP4 to support networking and mutual learning together with **science and data journalists and businesses in relevant sectors**. All these represent additional target audiences to be informed about the relevance of PartArt4OW, through PAIs news stories and impact findings.

Together with the above, the **general public** will be targeted to raise awareness on ocean and water challenges, maximise attendance to PAIs, events and to our festivals. A special attention will be paid to inform youth, especially showing them the potentialities of blue research and economy also for their study and work careers and because they are more flexible in terms of behaviours and are more likely to assume and spread sustainable behaviours.

All targets will be addressed also for showcasing PartArt4OW news and stories stemming from PAIs, acknowledging the positive impact of the project.

5. Communication Plan

This section focuses on communicating the project's goals, processes, and results to a wide audience, including the general public.

5.1 Objectives

- O1: Enhance the visibility of PartArt4OW goals, activities and outcomes, along its implementation;
- O2: Engage with stakeholders;
- O3: Bring attention to the three Open Calls;
- O4: Raise awareness about the PartArt4OW ecosystem and the toolkit;
- O5: Strengthen the understanding of art-science participatory processes by the wider society;
- O6: Communicate the benefits of art-science participatory processes;
- O7: Showcase the development and results of the PAIs throughout their lifetime;
- O8: Follow the activities of the Sailing Lab; and
- O9: Showcase the festivals and demo days to increase engagement attendance;
- O10: Present the results of the impact assessment, and
- O11: Promote and facilitate the ecosystem building through targeted communication and appropriate stakeholder management.

5.2 Key Messages

For the PartArt4OW project, each of the identified target audiences requires specific key messages tailored to their roles, interests, and potential contributions. The reasoning behind these messages is rooted in their capacity to influence, participate, or benefit from the project's outcomes. Here's an overview of the key messages for each audience:

Artists and Actors of the Cultural and Creative Sector

Artists are at the core of the project and need to understand the opportunity to engage creatively with ocean and water environmental issues. By highlighting how their work can have an impact on society and the environment, we aim to inspire participation in the

open calls and promote the matchmaking events. It will also encourage collaboration with scientists and citizens, positioning art as a tool for societal transformation and environmental stewardship.

Key Message:

"Your creativity and artistic talent can drive meaningful change in ocean and water protection. Join the PartArt4OW initiative to collaborate with scientists and communities in creating participatory art projects that foster marine literacy and sustainability."

Researchers/Innovators

Researchers and innovators may not traditionally see the arts as a mechanism for engagement, so the message needs to emphasise the value of transdisciplinary collaboration. By framing art as a way to connect emotionally with complex issues, researchers will be more likely to see this as an opportunity to extend the impact of their work.

The message should appeal to their interest in public engagement and innovative methods for communicating science.

Key Message:

"Explore new ways to engage the public with science through art. Collaborate with creative professionals to raise awareness on ocean and water challenges, generate emotional connections, and create innovative solutions for marine conservation."

Citizens/Communities and Civic Society Organizations

This message focuses on active engagement and participation, encouraging citizens and communities to take part in artistic initiatives, not just as observers but as co-creators. It emphasises collective action and personal investment in environmental protection, appealing to their sense of civic duty and community engagement. By highlighting the collaborative nature of the projects, it encourages a grassroots, inclusive approach to solving ocean and water challenges.

Key Message:

For Communities: "Be a part of the solution. Join artists, researchers, and local communities in creative projects that protect our oceans and waters. Together, we can raise awareness and build emotional connections to the environment for a more sustainable future."

For Civic Society: "PartArt4OW needs your leadership to drive change in sustainable water management across Europe! By working together with creative, scientific, and community stakeholders, you'll be instrumental in connecting scientific insights with community action. Be part of this movement to inspire impactful, evidence-based change!"

Policy Makers, Civic Servants, Funding Agencies, and Philanthropies

Policy makers and funding bodies are essential for scaling up initiatives. The message should focus on demonstrating the evidence-based outcomes of artistic and scientific collaborations, showing how these approaches can complement traditional methods of policy making and public awareness campaigns. By linking this work to larger policy objectives, like ocean restoration and climate resilience, the message encourages these stakeholders to invest in and endorse creative methods as part of sustainable governance.

Key Message:

"Supporting art and creativity in addressing ocean and water challenges can expand the impact of research and enhance public engagement. Help us scale these experimental methodologies for greater societal and environmental benefits."

Actors in the Blue Economy and Innovators

Blue economy actors need to see the value in integrating creativity and communities/citizen engagement into their work. This message positions art as a strategic tool to enhance corporate responsibility, foster innovation, and create new business models that align with environmental sustainability. It also highlights the

opportunity to leverage creative partnerships to boost public awareness and engagement in ways that can support blue economic growth.

Key Message:

"Collaborate with artists, the creative sector and local communities to foster a sustainable blue economy. Innovation and creativity can help shape a new narrative around marine health and create practical solutions for a thriving ocean-based economy."

Environmental NGOs and Advocacy Groups

For NGOs and advocacy groups, the message should emphasise how art can be a powerful tool for communication and engagement. By collaborating with artists, they can broaden the reach and emotional impact of their campaigns, making their causes more visible and relatable to the general public. The focus on synergies will resonate with these groups, as they are already mission-driven and are always seeking new ways to promote awareness and change.

Key Message:

"Art, creativity and citizen engagement can amplify your environmental message and mobilise broader public support for ocean and water conservation. Partner with PartArt4OW to enhance your advocacy through impactful, emotionally driven actions."

Topic-Related EU Projects

The focus here is on collaboration and mutual learning. Other EU-funded projects will be more inclined to engage if they see that the initiative aligns with their goals and can offer new insights or methodologies. Highlighting the potential for mutual benefit and knowledge sharing will strengthen networking and joint efforts. This message also emphasises the innovative aspect of the project, which will appeal to EU projects already engaged in cutting-edge science and advocacy. The general message here below will be adapted on a case by case basis to better reflect the potential synergies with the different projects.

Key Message:

"Join forces with PartArt4OW to foster a cross-sectoral approach to ocean and water protection. By integrating art, creativity and citizen engagement with science, we can co-create innovative solutions on a larger scale."

The General Public (Including Youth)

The message to the general public should be inspiring and accessible, encouraging participation in festivals, events, and PAIs. By focusing on engagement, creativity, and emotional connection to the oceans, this message aims to motivate people to get involved, especially youth, who are seen as change agents for future sustainable behaviours. For youth specifically, highlighting the connection between blue economy opportunities and their potential career paths adds a future-oriented, aspirational element.

Key Message:

"Discover how creativity can embrace science and community participation to protect our oceans and waters. Be part of the change by attending festivals, participating in community projects, and learning about the role of oceans in our future. Help us shape a sustainable world for generations to come."

5.3 Communication Channels

PartArt4OW will carry out its communication activities through different channels and with two different foci, one with a more generic view of communication, and another tailored to its different target audiences, considering their preferences, behaviours, and the type of content that will resonate with them.

PartArt4OW generic communication channels are:

- **Project Website & Blog:** The PartArt4OW website will serve as the main hub for information, hosting news, stories, event information, toolkits, and results. Regular blog updates will highlight progress and impact.
- **Email Campaigns:** Regular newsletters and email updates will be sent to a mailing list segmented by audience, ensuring each group receives targeted and relevant content.
- **Video Content:** Videos on platforms like YouTube or Vimeo will present the project's work in an accessible and engaging format.

PartArt4OW communication channels for the specific target audiences are:

Artists and Actors of the Cultural and Creative Sector

- **Social media (Instagram, Twitter/X, Facebook):** Visual and engaging platforms to promote open calls, matchmaking events, and showcase ongoing Participatory Art Initiatives (PAIs). Artists and creatives are highly active on these platforms, making it easier to attract their attention.
- **Artist Networks & Cultural Platforms:** Partnerships with online platforms and networks dedicated to the arts (e.g., ArtRabbit, Creative Europe, local art collectives, S+T+Ars) for targeted outreach.
- **Email Newsletters:** Subscription-based emails through arts and cultural networks to announce calls for participation and project milestones.
- **Artistic Events & Festivals:** In-person and virtual events such as art fairs, exhibitions, and creative festivals to create direct engagement with the artistic community. These also include those that the consortium partners will participate or be invited to.

Researchers/Innovators

- **Academic Networks and Journals:** Distribution of calls for participation, project updates, and outcomes through academic channels, such as research journals,

researchers' mailing lists, and research networks like ResearchGate or Academia.edu.

- **Conferences and Symposia:** Presenting at scientific and innovation-focused conferences (both online and in-person) to engage researchers in ocean and water-related issues.
- **LinkedIn and Twitter/X:** Professional networks for sharing project updates, research collaborations, and key findings, which are popular among academics and innovators.

Citizens/Communities and Civic Society Organizations

- **Local Media (Radio, Newspapers, TV):** Use local and regional media to reach communities, promoting open calls and participatory projects in accessible formats.
- **Community Events:** Organise or partner with local events, town hall meetings, and cultural gatherings to introduce PartArt4OW and gather participants for PAIs.
- **Social Media (Facebook, Instagram, YouTube):** Use these platforms to share engaging, visual content about ongoing projects and community participation, particularly emphasising storytelling to create emotional connections with ocean and water issues.
- **Public Spaces & Community Centres:** Flyers, posters, and other physical materials in community centres, libraries, schools, and civic organisation hubs to raise awareness and promote local participation.

Policy Makers, Civil Servants, Funding Agencies, and Philanthropies

- **Policy Briefs and Reports:** Use tailored communication materials such as policy briefs and impact assessment reports shared via email and during dedicated policy-oriented events.

- **High-Level Conferences & Policy Events:** Present findings and engage with policy makers at relevant international or regional conferences, such as the United Nations Ocean Conference or EU-funded policy events.
- **LinkedIn and Email Campaigns:** Targeted outreach to policy makers, civil servants, and philanthropists via professional platforms like LinkedIn, complemented by high-quality email campaigns with evidence-based content.

Actors in the Blue Economy and Innovators

- **Industry Conferences and Trade Shows:** Engage with blue economy actors at industry events, trade shows, and innovation summits to demonstrate the impact of creativity on sustainable marine business practices.
- **LinkedIn & Twitter/X:** Professional channels to share case studies, success stories, and partnership opportunities that highlight collaborations between artists and blue economy stakeholders.

Environmental NGOs and Advocacy Groups

- **Collaborative Campaigns:** Partner with NGOs on social media campaigns, cross-posting content, and aligning on joint communication efforts related to ocean and water protection.
- **Social Media (Twitter/X, Facebook):** Sharing advocacy content through NGOs' and PartArt4OW's social channels, amplifying the message to a wider activist audience.
- **Email Lists & Newsletters:** Target environmental organisations with updates on the project's progress, new opportunities for collaboration, and shared outcomes.
- **Joint Events:** Organise or participate in advocacy events, workshops, and public panel discussions with NGOs, where PartArt4OW's contributions to environmental issues can be highlighted.

Topic-Related EU Projects

- **EU Project Networks (CORDIS, Horizon Results Platform):** Share project outcomes and events through established EU project channels and networking events, leveraging synergies across projects. These include communities working in the European Blue Parks Projects, organisations participating in the EU4Ocean Platform and Light Houses projects on one hand, as well as projects associated with the New European Bauhaus initiative, S+T+Arts and Creative Europe projects. This will be carried out by the stakeholder mapping using FirstLife, an open-source mapping platform provided for free by the University of Turin, where social features of geo-referenced content creates an opportunity to enhance the connections, coordination and monitoring of community actions in Europe which combine art, science and participation for the ocean and waters.
- **Conferences & Research Collaborations:** Join topic-related panels or EU project fairs where mutual learning and collaborative opportunities can be facilitated.
- **Project Websites & Social Media:** Cross-promotion through each project's website, newsletters, and social media channels to share findings, toolkits, and events like the matchmaking sessions and PAIs.
- **EU Commission Platforms:** Use official EU platforms and partnerships, such as the European Commission's communication channels, to promote key findings and connect with other EU-funded initiatives.

General Public (Including Youth)

- **Social Media (Instagram, TikTok, YouTube):** Engage the general public, particularly youth, with visually appealing, creative, and emotionally compelling content, including videos, stories, and posts that highlight ocean challenges and the role of art in addressing them.
- **Public Events and Festivals:** PartArt4OW will hold three in-person festivals, scheduled to take place at the end of each acceleration round, to exhibit the outcomes of Participatory Art Initiatives (PAIs) and encourage their replication and expansion in other areas. The festivals will include art exhibits, live performances,

and showcases that blend science and art, drawing in both public audiences and professionals. Open to all, these events will spark curiosity and excitement, while also providing a global platform to promote PAI growth among international stakeholders, innovators, and philanthropic entities. Additionally, PAIs will host events in their chosen locations, actively supported and promoted by PartArt4OW. The PartArt4OW Sailing Lab will participate in select events, offering hands-on activities on and off board to raise awareness and highlight PAI projects in different regions. Lastly, project partners will attend various events to promote open calls and share project milestones.

- **Educational Institutions & Youth Organizations:** Partner with schools, universities, and youth organisations to promote PartArt4OW's initiatives, especially those focused on blue economy careers and environmental sustainability.

5.4 Communication Timeline

The communication plan for the **PartArt4OW** project spans the entire 30-month duration and integrates multiple channels and actions, aligned with the project's phases and objectives.

Below is a timeline and structure for the communication plan:

Month 1-5: Project Setup & Preparatory Phase

Objectives:

- Fine-tune communication and dissemination strategies (WP6)
- Establish necessary communication channels
- Begin stakeholder engagement

- Support the ecosystem building and ambassador network (ongoing throughout the whole project)

Key Actions:

- **Website Launch:** Create and launch a project website to serve as a primary hub for updates, resources, and the call documents.
- **Social Media Setup:** Set up dedicated accounts on platforms like Twitter (X), Instagram, LinkedIn, and Facebook to engage with different communities (artists, scientists, and policymakers).
- **Communication Strategy Finalization:** Refine and finalise communication strategies and plans (target audience definition, key messages, etc.).
- **Press Release:** Publish an introductory press release outlining the project objectives, partners, and timeline.
- **First Newsletter:** Send the first newsletter announcing the project launch and the upcoming open calls.
- **Stakeholder mapping and matrix:** Perform a stakeholder mapping exercise with the consortium partners, which will be updated regularly, where an analysis of their influence in the project is carried out. Additionally, create a stakeholder matrix to visualise their degree of influence and how they need to be kept engaged.

Month 6-7: First Open Call Launch

Objective: Disseminate open call to recruit Participatory Art Initiatives (PAIs)

Key Actions:

- **Call Announcement:** Release official open call documentation across digital platforms, including the project website and social media. The open calls will have a dedicated communication campaign, details are presented in section [5.5 Open Calls Communication Campaign](#).

- **Webinars & Matchmaking Sessions:** Host webinars to inform potential applicants about the call, and networking sessions for matchmaking.
- **Targeted Emails to Stakeholders:** Send out tailored communication to stakeholders from related EU projects and creative networks.
- **Content Creation (Videos, Graphics):** Develop promotional materials (e.g., explainer videos) to clarify the open call process.

Month 8-10: First Cohort Selection & Initial Mentorship

Objective: Publicise ongoing selection process, recruit mentors, and prepare for the accelerator program

Key Actions:

- **Update Communications:** Provide updates on the selection phase, showcasing the review process and highlighting consortium members.
- **Start of Accelerator Communications:** Create buzz around the first cohort of PAIs through newsletters and social media highlights.

Month 12-13: Second Open Call Launch

Similar to the previous Open Call Launch.

Month 14-16: Second Cohort Selection & Initial Mentorship

Similar to the First Cohort Selection & Initial Mentorship

Month 13-18: First Accelerator Program

Objective: Publicise the progress of PAIs, maintain engagement, and grow community awareness.

Key Actions:

- **Progress Updates on PAIs:** Regularly publish updates on the progress of PAIs through blog posts, social media updates, and newsletters.

- **Video Interviews & Case Studies:** Begin documenting PAIs in action, with interviews of artists, scientists, and citizens participating in the projects. The PAIs should take photo/video of their activities including short interviews and send it to Regenera, Raw-news will use this material in order to edit the 3 short videos and the last reportage (defined as a documentary in the GA). Raw-News will make further interviews to PAIs' Representatives when they will be on the two Barcelona demodays.
- **Sailing Lab Documentation:** As the Sailing Lab visits PAIs, releases visually engaging content (videos, photos) on social media and through dedicated events on the project website.
- **Interim Reports:** Publish interim reports on the progress of PAIs, share success stories, and maintain mentor engagement.

Month 17-18: Third Open Call Launch

Similar to the previous Open Call Launches.

Month 17-18: First PartArt4OW Festival

Objective: Showcase the results of PAIs from the first call.

Key Actions:

- **Festival Campaign:** Start a digital marketing campaign to promote the festival, using email, social media, and press releases.
- **Livestream Festival Events:** Broadcast key sessions, workshops, and exhibitions through livestreams on platforms like YouTube or Vimeo.
- **Festival Highlights:** Post-event coverage, including photo galleries, video recordings, and blog recaps on the website.

Month 19-21: Third Cohort Selection & Initial Mentorship

Similar to the First and the Second Cohort Selection & Initial Mentorship

Month 18-23: Second Accelerator Program

Similar to the First Accelerator Program

Month 22-23: Second PartArt4OW Festival

Similar to the Second PartArt4OW Festival

Month 23-28: Third Accelerator Program

Similar to the Second Accelerator Program

Month 27-28: Third PartArt4OW Festival

Similar to the Third PartArt4OW Festival

Month 29-30: Exploitation Report & Project Wrap-Up

Objective: Showcase final results, maximise dissemination, and wrap up the communication strategy.

Key Actions:

- **Toolkit & Final Reports:** Publicise the final project toolkit and outcome reports to stakeholders, policymakers, and the public.
- **Exploitation report:** As a deliverable to WP5, to present the exploitable results of the project.

Ongoing Communication Channels:

- **Website:** Central hub for project information, open calls, and resources.
- **Social Media (Twitter/X, LinkedIn, Instagram, Facebook):** For real-time updates, engagement, and wider outreach.
- **Newsletter:** Quarterly updates to stakeholders, participants, and partners.
- **Email Outreach:** Direct communication with stakeholders, collaborators, and participants.
- **Media Campaigns & PR:** Occasional press releases to media, leveraging major milestones (open calls, festivals, etc.).

5.5 Open Calls Communication Campaign

The open calls deserve a dedicated communication strategy to promote them effectively.

The communication campaign will follow these key phases:

1. Campaign Planning and Targeting

- **Goal Setting:** Establish clear goals for each open call, like the number and diversity of applicants, geographic reach, and quality of submissions.
- **Audience Definition:** Target artists, scientists, civic society actors, and community groups interested in ocean and water conservation across Europe.
- **Message Development:** Frame key messages around the themes of art, science, and community collaboration for ocean and water protection.

2. Content Creation and Branding

- **Visual Identity:** Develop a campaign identity that reflects PartArt4OW's values, incorporating vibrant visuals of oceans, communities, and art.
- **Content Strategy:** Create a mix of content types—videos, infographics, testimonials from past projects, and explainers on Participatory Art Initiatives (PAIs). We will consider both short, engaging content for social media and in-depth articles for interested participants.
- **Campaign Hashtag:** Introduce a unique hashtag like #PartArt4OW to consolidate the campaign on social media.

3. Promotion Channels and Tactics

- **Social Media:** Use Instagram, LinkedIn, and YouTube to target different audiences. Instagram can focus on artists and younger participants, while LinkedIn reaches professionals and potential partners.
- **Email Marketing:** Reach past applicants, collaborators, and interested organisations through newsletters and email outreach, offering updates on deadlines and requirements.

- **Press Outreach and Partnerships:** Issue press releases to European art, science, and sustainability publications. We may collaborate with influencers in the environmental and art spaces to amplify reach.
- **Website:** Highlight the open calls on the PartArt4OW website to reach communities and professional networks interested in sustainability, the arts, and science.

4. Engagement and Interaction

- **Webinars and Info Sessions:** Offer informative webinars on the open call process, PAI objectives, and PartArt4OW's goals, featuring past participants or program leaders.
- **Direct Engagement:** Actively respond to inquiries on social media, emails, and in Q&A sessions to provide clarity and encourage participation.

5. Monitoring and Adjustment

- Track engagement metrics (likes, shares, comments) on social media and open rates for email campaigns to gauge interest and adjust strategies.
- Gather early feedback to address any application process questions or barriers applicants may face.

5.6 Guiding principles

The communication strategy for **PartArt4OW** will be guided by the following core principles designed to maximise outreach, engagement, and the impact of its participatory art initiatives:

Clarity and Simplicity

Communicating complex ideas in a clear, simple, and digestible manner ensures accessibility to non-expert audiences, avoiding jargon or overly technical language and using straightforward and relatable terms that resonate with a broad range of

stakeholders. The use of clear visual aids (infographics, diagrams) will convey intricate concepts related to ocean preservation and participatory art initiatives.

Consistent Messaging

PartArt4OW will ensure all communication materials reflect a unified message aligned with the project's core objectives and mission. The project will develop a coherent narrative across all channels, reinforcing the importance of ocean protection, participatory art, and citizen engagement. It will maintain consistency in tone, voice, and branding to create a recognizable and cohesive identity for PartArt4OW.

Interactive and Engaging

The project will use interactive communication methods such as polls, Q&A sessions, or live webinars to engage our audience actively. It will encourage two-way communication where feedback, questions, and participation are welcomed and addressed promptly. It will incorporate storytelling, personal experiences, and testimonials to make the communication relatable and engaging.

Visual and Creative Storytelling

PartArt4OW will leverage the artistic nature of the project by incorporating visual storytelling—through images, videos, and creative art forms—to make communication more engaging. It will use multimedia content like short films, photo essays, and interactive online exhibitions to highlight project activities and impact. It will align the aesthetic presentation of communication materials with the project's themes of sustainability, creativity, and community engagement.

Transparency and Authenticity

PartArt4OW will communicate openly about project progress, challenges, successes, and lessons learned to build trust with stakeholders. It will share data, project updates, and results in a transparent way, ensuring accountability and fostering credibility. It will be honest about the scope and limitations of the project, avoiding over-promising while highlighting achievable and meaningful outcomes.

Timely and Responsive

PartArt4OW will ensure that communication is timely, with regular updates provided at key project milestones (e.g., launch of open calls, selection of initiatives, festivals), being responsive to questions, comments, and feedback from the audience, fostering a culture of open communication and dialogue. It will use social media and email effectively to provide real-time updates and respond to inquiries promptly.

Story-Driven Messaging

Part Art4OW will craft compelling stories around project participants, their experiences, and the positive impacts of their initiatives to make the communication more personal and relatable. By sharing the stories of local communities, artists, and scientists, it will humanise the project and make it emotionally resonant. It will highlight the journey of selected PAIs, from ideation to impact, through storytelling that emphasises transformation and progress.

Call to Action

PartArt4OW will always include clear calls to action in communication efforts, whether it's encouraging people to apply for open calls, attend events, or engage in dialogue. It will make it easy for stakeholders to take the next step by providing clear instructions on how to participate, collaborate, or learn more. It will use action-oriented language to inspire and mobilise audiences, encouraging active involvement in ocean and water preservation through art.

Inclusivity

The project will foster the engagement of underrepresented minorities and communities in the PAIs, this being one of the qualifying aspects during the proposals' evaluation process. They will be encouraged to include them directly in artistic processes, and provide tailored training for underrepresented groups. Festivals and events should prioritise accessibility and welcome diverse participation, while regular feedback mechanisms can ensure the project's activities meet the needs of all stakeholders.

6. Dissemination Plan

Dissemination focuses on sharing the results with stakeholders who can directly benefit from or build upon the project's findings.

6.1 Objectives

Here are some dissemination objectives for the PartArt4OW project, centred on sharing and distributing project results and outcomes:

O1: Share Project Results: Disseminate comprehensive reports and findings from the 19 Participatory Art Initiatives (PAIs) to a wide audience, including stakeholders in the artistic, scientific, and civic sectors.

O2: Promote Awareness of Impact: Highlight the qualitative and quantitative impacts of the PAIs on ocean and water challenges, ensuring that stakeholders understand the value added by interdisciplinary and participatory approaches.

O3: Foster Community Engagement: Ensure that local communities and relevant stakeholders have access to the project's outcomes, enabling them to engage with and contribute to ongoing initiatives.

O4: Create Knowledge Transfer Opportunities: Develop tools and resources, such as the PartArt4OW toolkit, that facilitate the sharing of best practices and lessons learned from the project, enabling other organisations to replicate successful initiatives. Facilitate knowledge transfer to the scientific community, industry, and policymakers.

O5: Facilitate Networking: Connect project partners with other stakeholders, such as policymakers, funding bodies, and environmental NGOs, to share insights and foster collaboration based on project outcomes.

O6: Enhance Visibility of PAIs: Actively promote the activities and results of the PAIs through various communication channels, including social media, newsletters, and events, to maximise their reach and impact.

O7: Provide Access to Educational Resources: Disseminate educational materials and outcomes related to ocean and water literacy to schools, community

organisations, and the general public, enhancing awareness and understanding of these critical issues.

O8: Encourage Feedback and Reflection: Create mechanisms for stakeholders to provide feedback on the project's results, fostering a culture of reflection and continuous improvement based on shared outcomes.

6.2 Key Dissemination Activities

Here are the main dissemination activities for the PartArt4OW project, designed to effectively share information about the project, its results, and outcomes:

Publications and Reports: Develop and distribute comprehensive reports detailing the results and impacts of the Participatory Art Initiatives (PAIs). Create case studies showcasing successful PAIs and their contributions to ocean and water challenges.

Workshops and Conferences: Partners will take part in workshops and conferences to present findings and share experiences with stakeholders in the artistic, scientific, and civic sectors. Facilitate panel discussions and presentations at relevant events to engage with a wider audience.

Social Media Campaigns: Utilise platforms like Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and LinkedIn to share project milestones, achievements, and updates. Create engaging content, such as infographics, videos, and stories from participants, to reach a broader audience.

Newsletters: Publish a quarterly newsletter highlighting project progress, key findings, and upcoming events to keep stakeholders informed. Feature stories from participants and stakeholders, showcasing their involvement and the impact of the project.

Dedicated Project Website: Develop and maintain a user-friendly website that includes a section for sharing resources and results like the PartArt4OW toolkit, deliverables, PAIs outcomes, and other educational materials.

Participatory Events and Festivals: Organise public festivals and events to showcase the artistic outputs of the PAIs and engage the community in discussions about ocean and water challenges. Include interactive exhibits, performances, and workshops to attract diverse audiences.

Press Releases and Media Engagement: Issue press releases to announce key findings, milestones, and events, reaching out to local and national media for coverage. Collaborate with media partners to produce articles, podcasts, and documentaries that highlight the project and its impact.

Networking Opportunities: Facilitate networking events to connect project partners with policymakers, funders, and other stakeholders to discuss collaborative opportunities based on project outcomes. Engage with existing networks and platforms to share results and foster partnerships.

Community Engagement Initiatives: Develop outreach programs to engage local communities, schools, and organisations in discussions about ocean and water issues and the project's findings. Create opportunities for community members to participate in discussions and activities related to the PAIs.

6.3 Dissemination Channels

In addition to the abovementioned activities (community events and festivals, conferences and workshops, etc.) the project will utilise dissemination channels such as: **academic journals and conferences** to publish research findings to reach the research community; **leverage partnerships** with other organisations, NGOs, and stakeholders to disseminate information through their channels and networks; **collaborate with media outlets** (e.g., newspapers, magazines, radio, and TV) for broader coverage of project activities and outcomes; use platforms such as **LinkedIn groups, research forums**, and **community boards** to share project updates and engage with specific interest groups; attend **networking events** to connect with policymakers, funders, and stakeholders interested in the project's themes; utilise platforms such as **Zenodo**, GitHub, or other

open-access repositories to share research data, publications, project reports, and artistic outputs; and ensure all materials are tagged appropriately to enhance discoverability and allow for easy access by researchers, practitioners, and the general public.

6.4 Dissemination Timeline

Although the communication timeline already contains most of the dissemination activities, here the focus is on highlighting the specific dissemination activities across time:

Phase 1: Project Initiation (Months 1-6): After the delivery of the DEC Plan with the initial dissemination strategy and communication plan, the dissemination activities will focus on: the identification, mapping and initial engagement of key stakeholders for dissemination efforts; beginning the outreach to local communities and organisations; the creation of an initial blog post discussing the project objectives and importance; and at the month 6, the evaluation of the dissemination efforts from the first six months, adjusting strategies based on feedback and engagement metrics.

Phase 2: Implementation of PAIs (Months 7-28): The dissemination efforts will be focused on showcasing aspects and results of the selected PAIs: their objectives, via press releases and social media; publishing of detailed profiles of each PAI on the website; sharing interim results from PAIs through newsletters and updates on social media; conducting a webinar highlighting successful strategies and practices; uploading results, research data, and artistic outputs to public repositories (Zenodo); attending conferences and workshops where the results of the PAIs are presented; creating infographics summarising PAI results and impact; conduct final evaluations of the PAIs and prepare reports on their outcomes; share the results with networks; and share success stories and case studies through newsletters and social media.

Phase 3: Project Conclusion and Legacy (Months 28-30): Analyse the overall impact of the project and compile findings into a final report; disseminate findings to stakeholders through targeted communication; finalise the toolkit for other actors interested in

implementing PAIs-like projects; promote the toolkit through newsletters and social media; organise the concluding festivals to showcase PAIs results; engage local communities and stakeholders in discussions about project outcomes; publish a comprehensive report summarising project achievements and lessons learned; create and distribute a project booklet or summary brochure; share project findings and outputs on public repositories and academic journals; and maintain engagement with stakeholders through ongoing newsletters and social media.

7. Exploitation Plan

This section outlines how the project results will be used beyond the life of the project for societal or economic benefit. This will be updated throughout the project to reflect new findings, and will be presented in a final Sustainability and Exploitation Plan as deliverable 5.3.

7.1 Objectives

The main objectives of the exploitation activities for the **PartArt4OW** project will be focused on ensuring the practical application and sustained impact of its outcomes, particularly by fostering collaboration, uptake, and replication of innovative ideas. Below are the primary objectives with their exploitable outcomes:

O1: Maximise the Long-Term Impact of Project Results: Ensure the key exploitable results (KERs) of the project are applied across industries, communities, and public institutions. This will secure long-term benefits beyond the project's lifetime. **Outcome:** Sustainable integration of interdisciplinary solutions into practical use by businesses, educational institutions, and civic society.

O2: Facilitate Cross-Sectoral Collaboration: Strengthen cooperation between the artistic, scientific, and industrial sectors, enabling the transfer of knowledge and co-creation of new solutions to tackle ocean and water challenges. **Outcome:** Increase partnerships between creative industries, businesses in the blue economy, and research institutions.

O3: Support Policy Development and Influence Decision-Making: Provide policymakers with evidence-based insights and experimental methodologies developed through the PAIs to support sustainable ocean and water governance. **Outcome:** Influence policy changes and decisions aligned with sustainable environmental practices and interdisciplinary approaches.

O4: Promote the Replication and Scaling-Up of PAIs: Encourage the replication of successful PAIs in other regions or sectors, allowing broader adoption and implementation of the project's innovative approaches. **Outcome:** Widespread adoption of the PAIs model, enhancing the project's impact across Europe and beyond.

7.2 Key Exploitation Outputs, Activities, Pathways and Stakeholders

The programme itself will produce six types of **exploitable outputs**, required in the Grant Agreement:

- (i) processes and tools for the open call;
- (ii) learning resources developed for the accelerator;
- (iii) PartArt4OW toolkit;
- (iv) PartArt4OW impact assessment methodology;
- (v) PartArt4OW Sailing Lab to promoting ocean and water literacy; and
- (vi) The PartArt4OW trademark and festival, as a reference yearly event for the European ecosystem.

The **exploitation activities** for PartArt4OW will focus on ensuring the practical use and application of the project's outputs (results, methodologies, and innovations). These activities would aim to maximise the long-term benefits of the project outcomes across various sectors (e.g., industry, academia, policy-making, and civil society). Below are potential exploitation activities, some of them are required in the Grant Agreement, here we are mentioning all the potential activities we could develop during the project lifetime:

- **Creation of the PartArt4OW Toolkit:** Develop a toolkit that includes best practices, methodologies, and lessons learned from the PAIs and partArt4OW. This toolkit would be designed for replication and adaptation by external stakeholders (e.g., civic society, businesses, policymakers). **Exploitation Pathway:** Make the toolkit accessible through the project's website and key online

repositories, distribute it at conferences, and share it with industry bodies and policymakers.

- **Scaling PAIs Across Europe:** Replicate the successful PAIs in other regions, encouraging cross-border collaboration and the transfer of knowledge and technologies. **Exploitation Pathway:** Collaborate with local authorities, NGOs, and creative hubs to transfer the PAIs' models to new regions.
- **Public-Private Partnerships:** Develop partnerships between public institutions and private companies for co-financing the long-term continuation of successful PAIs beyond the project's funding period. **Exploitation Pathway:** Approach private foundations, corporate sponsors, and public bodies to develop joint ventures or co-funded programs.
- **Use of Sailing Lab as a Knowledge Exchange Platform:** Utilise the **PartArt4OW Sailing Lab** to conduct workshops, onboard exhibitions, and travelling events that spread the project's findings across Europe's coastal regions. **Exploitation Pathway:** Organise collaborative events between artists, scientists, and local stakeholders, focusing on practical solutions for ocean and water management.
- **Open Access to Scientific Data and Artistic Outputs:** Ensure that all scientific data, reports, and artistic works generated by the PAIs are openly accessible. **Exploitation Pathway:** Publish data in open-access repositories, promote artistic outputs through online platforms, and collaborate with open-source communities.
- **Festivals and Public Events:** Continue organising festivals and events that showcase PAIs to local communities, business leaders, and policymakers. **Exploitation Pathway:** Develop long-term collaborations with cultural institutions, museums, and festivals to integrate project outputs into their programs.

The **key exploitation stakeholders** for the PartArt4OW project are those who can benefit from, apply, or further develop the project's results. They are also responsible for ensuring that the project's innovations and methodologies have a lasting impact. These stakeholders can be grouped into nine categories:

- **Artists and Cultural and Creative Sectors:** They may apply innovative methods of combining arts and science to raise awareness and inspire action on ocean and water issues. They could utilise the interdisciplinary approaches developed in PAIs to drive creative works, exhibitions, or public engagement projects. Examples: Independent artists, cultural organisations, creative industries.
- **Scientific Community and Researchers:** They may integrate artistic approaches into scientific methodologies, particularly in environmental and oceanic research. They could collaborate with artists and cultural actors to enhance science communication and public engagement, advancing research impact. Examples: Marine biologists, environmental scientists, research institutes, universities.
- **Policymakers and Government Bodies:** They may leverage evidence and outcomes from the project to inform policy-making in ocean governance and sustainable development. They could use results to create or adapt policies and regulations that support interdisciplinary, participatory initiatives in environmental governance. Examples: National and regional governments, EU policymakers, local authorities.
- **Businesses and Innovators in the Blue Economy:** They may collaborate with creative and research sectors to develop sustainable practices and innovations for ocean and water resource management. They could integrate sustainable, creative solutions from PAIs into products, services, and business models. Examples: Companies in the blue economy, maritime industries, technology developers.
- **Environmental NGOs and Advocacy Groups:** They may use project outcomes to further their advocacy for ocean conservation and sustainable water management. They could engage communities, build campaigns, and drive citizen participation in ocean literacy and action, leveraging the innovative methods from the project. Examples: Conservation organisations, grassroots movements, NGOs focused on biodiversity and climate action.
- **Educational Institutions and Training Organizations:** They may embed the project's findings and methodologies in educational programs, helping to build

future talent in the areas of environmental stewardship and participatory science. They could develop training and academic programs that teach interdisciplinary approaches to ocean and water challenges, blending arts, science, and technology. Examples: Universities, vocational schools, online learning platforms.

- **Philanthropies and Funding Bodies:** They may identify and support interdisciplinary projects that align with the project's mission of ocean conservation and sustainability. They could fund and scale up projects modelled on the successful PAIs, supporting long-term environmental and social impact. Examples: Private philanthropies, international development funds, government grants.
- **Citizens and Community Groups:** They may act as direct beneficiaries and participants in PAIs, contributing to ocean literacy and local conservation efforts. They could engage with and spread knowledge on ocean challenges, contributing to the sustainability of local water ecosystems. Examples: Local communities, grassroots movements, citizen science volunteers.
- **Media and Communication Professionals:** They may amplify the reach of the project's results, fostering public discourse on the importance of ocean conservation and interdisciplinary collaboration. They could use storytelling, media campaigns, and documentaries to spread the message of PartArt4OW and its successes. Examples: Journalists, social media influencers, documentary filmmakers.

7.3 Exploitation Timeline

Year 1: Initial Set-up and Stakeholder Engagement

Months 1-5:

- **Collaboration with Industry:** Identify key industry partners in the blue economy, sustainable technologies, and creative industries.
- **Policy Influence:** Start engagement with local, regional, and national policymakers.

Months 6-8: Building Momentum and Dissemination

- **Integration into Educational Curricula:** Establish contacts with universities and vocational institutions.
- **Collaboration with Industry:** Begin co-creation workshops with industry partners to tailor methodologies to real-world applications.

Months 9-12: Key Exploitation Activities

- **Festivals and Public Events:** Plan the first festival showcasing PAIs, involving key stakeholders like industry leaders, researchers, and policymakers. Repeat this in the following festivals and events.

Year 2: Broadening Reach and Deepening Impact

Months 13-18:

- **Scaling PAIs Across Europe:** Begin discussions with new regions and local authorities for replicating successful PAIs.
- **Public-Private Partnerships:** Develop proposals for co-funding programs and joint ventures to sustain PAIs.

Months 19-30: Ensuring Long-term Sustainability

- **Public-Private Partnerships:** Formalise partnerships with private foundations, companies, and public bodies for long-term sustainability.
- **Open Access to Data and Artistic Outputs:** Continue publishing scientific data and artistic outputs in open-access repositories.
- **Use of Sailing Lab as Knowledge Platform:** Organise workshops and travelling exhibitions through the Sailing Lab to engage with new communities and spread project findings.

- **Create final project report on exploitation activities:** Deliver a final report with the identified exploitation activities that need to continue beyond the end of the project, which corresponds to Deliverable 5.3 “Sustainability and Exploitation Plan”.
- **Toolkit Launch:** Finalise and release the toolkit on the project website and repositories (Zenodo). Distribute toolkit to industry partners, educational institutions, and policymakers at conferences.

Ongoing Activities Throughout the Project

- **Monitoring Success Metrics:** Regular tracking of KPIs (toolkit downloads, industry partnerships, educational engagements, etc.) to adjust strategies as needed.
- **Sustaining Long-term Impact:** Maintain and grow partnerships with stakeholders in academia, industry, and policy even after the project concludes, ensuring the ongoing use of PartArt4OW methodologies and innovations.

8. The Sailing Lab

The Sailing Lab in the PartArt4OW project will act as a key platform for communication, dissemination, and exploitation efforts, playing an essential role in showcasing the project's outcomes to a broad audience. It will be a flexible and powerful tool for conveying PartArt4OW's core messages, ensuring that its results are shared and utilised in a way that is both inclusive and wide-reaching.

Communication:

The Sailing Lab will act as a **mobile exhibition and event space**, travelling across various coastal regions in Europe. It may host a series of **interactive workshops, presentations, and exhibitions** that will engage local communities, artists, scientists, and stakeholders. Through these activities, the Sailing Lab will highlight the project's **objectives, methodologies, and successes**, allowing participants to explore ocean and water challenges creatively and scientifically. The communication efforts will focus on creating immersive experiences that foster dialogues between diverse stakeholders, enhancing public awareness and understanding of the project's mission.

Dissemination:

The Sailing Lab will support dissemination by **showcasing outputs** such as scientific data, artistic works, and community-led solutions from the PAIs. These outputs will be displayed during the Sailing Lab's stops in the selected locations, including video or photographic showcases. The dissemination will be further enhanced by **media coverage** of Sailing Lab events, **social media campaigns** (published by RegNet), and may include **live-streaming** sessions (in cooperation with RegNet) to reach a broader audience. Moreover, the Sailing Lab will contribute to **local outreach efforts**, helping to distribute PartArt4OW's findings, toolkits, and other resources through face-to-face interactions with stakeholders and citizens.

Exploitation:

As part of exploitation activities, the Sailing Lab will facilitate partnerships by connecting local governments, businesses, civil society actors, and researchers interested in adopting or scaling the project's findings.

9. KPIs and Monitoring tools

To effectively monitor and evaluate the communication, exploitation and dissemination activities of PartArt4OW, a set of realistic Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and their monitoring measures are defined. These KPIs will track the success of various communication efforts in reaching target audiences, creating awareness, and achieving broader project goals.

Table 2: KPIs and monitoring tools

Awareness and Reach			
What	KPI	Target	Monitoring tool
Website Traffic	Number of unique visitors to the project website	1,500 unique visitors within the first year, 3,000 by the end of the project.	Google Analytics or similar platform.
Social Media Engagement	Number of followers and engagement rate (likes, shares, comments).	1,000 followers across platforms by the end of the project; engagement rate of at least 5%.	Platform-specific analytics (Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn).
Media Coverage	Number of mentions in major media outlets (e.g., Al Jazeera, BBC, National Geographic).	20 media mentions per year.	Media monitoring tools (Meltwater, Google Alerts).
Press Releases	Number of press releases issued and number of media pickups	At least 4 press releases per year with 30% pickup rate by media.	Media tracking, PR software
Open Call outreach	Number of actors reached	>10k in total for the three open calls	Application portal analytics, mailing list, social media followers
Newsletter	Number of newsletters	10 newsletters published	Number of newsletters published
Festivals and Public Events Attendance	Number of attendees at the three festivals and other public events	>200 attendees per festival	Event registration and attendee tracking
Content and Dissemination			
What	KPI	Target	Monitoring tool
Content Production	Number of blog posts, podcasts, videos, and other content pieces produced	30 blog posts, 10 podcasts, 3 short videos (3-5 mins each), 1 project video documentary (15 to 30 mins) and 3 photo reportages over the project duration	Website and content management platform
Newsletter Engagement	Newsletter open rate and click-through rate (CTR)	30% open rate, 10% CTR	Email marketing platform analytics
Sailing Lab Documentation	Number of multimedia pieces (photos, video-news, interviews and feature-stories) produced and shared from the Sailing Lab	At least 3 multimedia pieces per PAI location visited	Internal tracking

Research papers	Number of publications in open-access platforms (Zenodo, ResearchGate).	At least 3 papers published by the end of the project.	Track publication uploads and downloads from the repositories.
Presenting at Scientific Conferences	Number of conference presentations.	At least 5 presentations over the course of the project.	Keep a record of conference participation and presentation materials.
Internal KPIs			
What	KPI	Target	Monitoring tool
CDE Plan Execution	Percentage of planned communication and dissemination activities executed on time.	90% of CD activities completed according to the timeline	CD Matrix and internal monitoring tools
Partner Participation in CDE Activities	Number of consortium partners actively participating in communication and dissemination activities	All project partners actively contributing to at least 3 communication activities annually	CD Matrix tracking

10. Monitoring and Evaluation

PartArt4OW has created a communication activities tracking folder where partners will locate their communication and dissemination activities by uploading relevant documents and files and completing an excel sheet with description of the activities and data necessary to track the KPIs, according to the KPIs defined in section [9. KPIs and Monitoring tools](#). Once a month this material and information will be uploaded to the EC portal section of Communication Activities reporting. All the monitoring tools will also be located in this folder for continuous checking.

11. Tools and Channels

11.1 Visual identity

PartArt4OW visual identity includes a logo, branding guidelines, templates for internal communication and external communication activities. The brand guideline is available here: [PartArt4OW Branding Guidelines 2024](#). It includes the requirements for use of the EC commission logo and disclaimer, the UN Ocean Decade logo, and the Horizon Europe and Mission Ocean logos.

11.2 Website

The PartArt4OW website will be launched in November 2024 and it represents the main window for communication and dissemination actions. At this first stage it shows a simple menu that will get more complex as the different phases of the project unfold. Deliverable 6.2 explains its rationale and production.

New pages will include the open calls, the accelerator, the funded PAIs, the Sailing Lab, a repository of learning resources (virtual bootcamp), our publications and deliverables, news from the PAIs, as well dashboards with open call stats and impact data.

The website will feature a virtual bootcamp containing freely accessible education resources. Some of these will be created for the accelerator in WP2, others will be from prior or related projects of the PartArt4OW consortium and our collaborations, including IMPETUS, the updated ACTION toolkit, the Collective Intelligence Design Playbook, D-NOSES and NEWSERA. Smooth alignment, cross reference, and cross-pollination with the EU Citizen-Science platform will be constantly pursued.

11.3 Social media

Social media requires continuous effort and monitoring of its performance. PartArt4OW will concentrate its initiatives on its Instagram, LinkedIn, and YouTube accounts. Additionally, we plan to utilise advertising and campaigns to promote open calls and significant project milestones. The figures below present some of the profile pictures and banners and the look of the Instagram feed.

Fig.2: Instagram (and YouTube) profile picture

Fig.3: Instagram Feed Style

Fig.5: Banner for LinkedIn account

Partners will be encouraged to use and share information about the project through their institutional Facebook and Instagram accounts.

11.4 ZENODO

Zenodo is a versatile open-access repository established through the European OpenAIRE initiative and managed by CERN. It enables researchers to upload a variety of research-related digital assets, including papers, datasets, software, reports, and more. The PartArt4OW project has set up an account on Zenodo and has created a dedicated community to share its reports, outcomes, and communication materials, thereby extending its visibility beyond the project's website. A link to the Zenodo repository will be prominently featured on the project's website.

11.5 Promotional materials for open calls and the Sailing Lab

Open calls: PartArt4OW will create and produce a variety of promotional materials, as detailed below. This list is not exhaustive. The initial call for submissions is scheduled to open at the beginning of February and will close at the end of March. To ensure that all materials are prepared on time, a production calendar will be established in the project's shared folder.

1. Digital postcards
2. A video animation explaining the process for proposal submission
3. PPT presentations presenting the call
4. A dedicated section on the website as well as promotional banners will be produced with the support of a professional designer and circulated amongst the partners.

The Sailing Lab: PartArt4OW will produce material for the promotion of the activities of the Sailing Lab, to inform of its departure, the route and dates, and what PAIs are visiting the different ports where it will dock. We will develop a video animation presenting its route and instructions for the visiting PAIs.

11.6 Publications

- **Scientific publications** resulting from project efforts, such as those related to action research in WP4 or the impact assessment methods developed in WP5, will be published as open access and submitted to relevant conferences and academic journals.
- **Press releases** will be distributed during significant project milestones (such as open calls, accelerator launches, and award announcements) to enhance visibility and engage traditional media outlets. These press releases will form part of a broader media relations strategy designed to attract media attention, establish reliable relationships with journalists, and promote visibility to draw applicants for the accelerator and awards.
- The project will also develop a **newsletter** to keep its audience updated. Additionally, it will monitor other newsletters where project-related information can be shared. For instance, outreach will be made to the ECSA newsletter to significantly increase reach.

11.7 Infographics

A collection of infographics for dissemination will be created at various phases of the project. In November, the partners will establish a calendar outlining the requirements for these infographics.

12. Final Remarks

This plan serves as a roadmap document. Its successful execution will rely on the collaborative efforts of all partners involved. The plan will be regularly reviewed and modified to address current needs and any external circumstances that may arise. Consequently, it should be viewed as a dynamic document.